

Gender Disparities in Brokerage of Scientific Collaboration

Jan Bachman

Complexity Science Hub

Structural inequalities between men and women persist in academia. The "glass ceiling effect" is one such inequality. It describes an invisible barrier that blocks women and other marginalized groups from accessing highly ranked positions in their respective fields [1]. Naturally, a substantial amount of research has tried to identify this phenomenon and its causes. Beyond other gender disparities, such as gender asymmetries in family obligations, so-called "old boy networks" have been identified as a potential explanation [2]. These networks consist of informal, social connections among typically highly ranked, senior male professionals. Through them, crucial information, such as job openings and referrals are propagated [3, 4]. Existing work has shown the existence of these networks, highlighted their importance, and dipped into understanding their structure and emergence [5, 6].

In social network theory, "tertius iungens brokerage", refers to the process in which a broker entity mediates between two other locally close or already connected parties by facilitating their collaboration in a brief or sustained matter [7]. Recent literature has focused mostly on gender disparities in the "tertius gaudens brokerage" process where the broker bridges large network distances instead [8, 9].

Understanding gender biases in the tertius iungens case could partially explain the existence and long-lived persistence of structural gender inequalities in academia. For instance, introducing preferably young male scientists to existing old boy networks would gate-keep women from similar opportunities. A study of gender biases in tertius iungens brokerage which incorporates large temporal & population scales is still missing.

To close this gap, we propose a temporal network analysis to understand the role of female and men brokers in academic collaboration networks. In particular, we focus on the temporal formation of triangles and their gender composition as "temporal motifs", i.e., small building blocks of the network. The results may reveal gender biases in who introduces whom to whom.

Method

We consider a large-scale, temporally growing co-authorship network from over 600000 articles published by the American Physical Society (APS). In this dataset, 34596 (15%) women and 195 490 (85%) men co-authoring a paper between 1893 and 2020 are connected pairwise at the time of publication. We capture the formation

Figure 1. (A) Temporal formation of triangles between nodes a , b and c over three distinct points in time $t_1 < t_2 < t_3$. Here, node b is the broker, and we differentiate whether b participates in the last collaboration (bottom) or not (top). To capture the initiation of each contact, we count only the first occurrence of each link. (B) Including all possible gender compositions, we distinguish a total of 16 motifs. Note that cases of semi-distinct temporality ($t_i \leq t_j$) are left out for simplicity here, but will be considered in the final manuscript.

of triangles in this network via 16 temporal network motifs. Such motifs are equivalence classes of small subgraphs, defined by the number of participating nodes and the temporal order of their links [10]. If two authors a and c , who share a mutual former colleague b , collaborate, they close a triangle in the network (see Figure 1.A, top). We focus on motifs involving three authors and their publication activities up to the point where all three of them have collaborated. Moreover, we enforce a temporal separation between each of the three publications ($t_1 < t_2 < t_3$) to distinguish the three roles among the participating authors. We refer to author b as "broker", as they collaborated with a and c before they published together for the first time, potentially introducing them to one another.

Moreover, we differentiate whether b participated in the final paper that introduced a and c (see Figure 1.A, bottom). Adding the authors' gender as binary node labels and propagating it over the three nodes produces a total of 16 motifs (see Figure 1.B).

Results

We use these motifs to identify gender biases in the brokerage process. For this, we partition the analysis into two parts: first, we analyze the formation process in time and gender composition; second, we investigate its potential impact and scientists' career.

Motif formation: Following the motif specification, we define the opening time of a triangle as the time between the first two collaborations $\Delta t_{open} = t_2 - t_1$ and its closure time as the time delta between the last two links $\Delta t_{close} = t_3 - t_2$. In Figure 2, we report the ratio difference of the time intervals for the two closure types and the gender of the broker b . The value tends towards zero if both intervals are equally long, or towards ± 1 the more one quantity is larger than the other. Albeit finding no strong disparity between men and women, there is a clear distinction between the two motif types. When the broker participates in the final closure event, $M_{(abc)}$, the closure time is generally lower.

Beyond the speed of formation, understanding

Figure 2. (Left) Comparison between triangle opening and closure time. Values of zero indicate equal intervals. Values towards +1 (-1) indicate that the closing occurs faster (slower) than the opening. The x-axis differentiates whether the broker b participates in the final closure event $M_{(abc)}$ or not M_{abc} . Colors indicate the gender of the broker b . Irrespective of the broker's gender, triangles close faster when b participates in the closure. (Right) The z-scores of each temporal motif (connecting lines for visual aid). A value of zero indicates that the null hypothesis could not be rejected. As most values are well above or below zero, we conclude that motif counts do not solely depend on the difference in gender-group sizes.

Figure 3. Career age (median and quantiles) per author role and motif. The global median per gender of all authors with more than two publications is indicated by the horizontal dotted lines. Each bar group represents the career lengths of all authors who participated in the closure process as a , b or c in that order. Most notably, there appears to be a qualitative difference between the two closure types. In M_{abc} , authors a and b are older than c , whereas only b is oldest in $M_{(abc)}$.

fundamental. To account for disparities in group sizes (women being the numerical minority), we create 500 permutations of the network by shuffling the gender attribute across all authors. As this preserves everything besides the individual gender assignment, we use it to test whether the observed motif counts depend solely on the disparity in the overall gender group sizes (see [11] for a similar application). From the permutations, we infer distributions of motif counts (or other metrics) based on the specified null model. We compute z-scores to compare the observed motif counts to the distribution retrieved by the gender-label permutations and find that most scores strongly differ from zero ($|z| > 0$, see Figure 2). Thus, we conclude that motifs do not only depend on the group size disparity. This observation is not surprising, given the likely presence of other dynamics such as changes in group sizes and their activity in time.

Further investigations will be guided toward utilizing null models which account for additional confounders, such as disparities in group size and productivity.

Broker effect: Finally, we make a first attempt toward quantifying the impact that the brokerage process has on the participants' careers. Prior research has found that gender disparities in impact and productivity disappear when

accounting for differences in career lengths [12]. Understanding how brokerage correlates with a scientist's academic longevity would hence give insight into multiple inequalities. In line with [12], we consider only scientists who had their last publication five years before the end of our recording. This (partially) accounts for temporal boundary effects which would falsely shorten career lengths for scientists who are active toward the end of the dataset. We collect the career length as the difference between the first and last publication dates of the remaining authors. Figure 3 shows the differences for each role and motif.

Most interestingly, we observe qualitative differences between the two closure types. When brokers b participate in the closure collaboration, $M_{(abc)}$, they typically have the highest overall career age among the three authors. When a and c collaborate for the first time without the broker b , M_{abc} , it is a and b who have the highest longevity. This could indicate that the first case describes brokerage in which a senior broker b introduces two junior students a and c . As this collaboration might require b 's expertise, it could lead to a joint publication. In the other case, after b introduces a and c , a could take over the senior role. This, in return, connects back to the sustained versus brief brokerage distinction in the literature [7]. We note that this is only the first step of the analysis in that direction. Before

making any conclusion, we will investigate this observation more thoroughly in the final contribution.

References

1. Glass Ceiling Commission, U. Good for Business: Making Full Use of the Nation's Human Capital (US Government Printing Office, Mar. 1, 1995).
2. Maheshwari, M. & Lenka, U. An Integrated Conceptual Framework of the Glass Ceiling Effect. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance* 9, 372–400. (2022) (Jan. 1, 2022).
3. Oakley, J. G. Gender-Based Barriers to Senior Management Positions: Understanding the Scarcity of Female CEOs. *Journal of Business Ethics* 27, 321–334. (2022) (Oct. 1, 2000).
4. Cooper Jackson, J. Women Middle Managers' Perception of the Glass Ceiling. *Women in Management Review* 16, 30–41. (2022) (Jan. 1, 2001).
5. Van Helden, D. L., den Dulk, L., Steijn, B. & Vernooij, M. W. Gender, Networks and Academic Leadership: A Systematic Review. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 17411432211034172. (2022) (Aug. 16, 2021).
6. McDonald, S. What's in the "Old Boys" Network? Accessing Social Capital in Gendered and Racialized Networks. *Social Networks* 33, 317–330. (2022) (Oct. 1, 2011).
7. Obstfeld, D. Social Networks, the Tertius Iungens Orientation, and Involvement in Innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 50, 100–130. JSTOR: 30037177. (2023) (2005).
8. Fang, R., Zhang, Z. & Shaw, J. D. Gender and Social Network Brokerage: A Meta-Analysis and Field Investigation. *The Journal of Applied Psychology* 106, 1630–1654. pmid: 33030920 (Nov. 2021).
9. Brands, R. A. & Mehra, A. Gender, Brokerage, and Performance: A Construal Approach. *Academy of Management Journal* 62, 196–219. (2022) (Feb. 2019).
10. Kovanen, L., Karsai, M., Kaski, K., Kertész, J. & Saramäki, J. Temporal Motifs in Time-Dependent Networks. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment* 2011, P11005. (2022) (Nov. 2011).
11. Kovanen, L., Kaski, K., Kertész, J. & Saramäki, J. Temporal Motifs Reveal Homophily, Gender-Specific Patterns, and Group Talk in Call Sequences. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, 18070–18075. pmid: 24145424. (2022) (Nov. 5, 2013).
12. Huang, J., Gates, A. J., Sinatra, R. & Barabási, A.-L. Historical Comparison of Gender Inequality in Scientific Careers across Countries and Disciplines. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117, 4609–4616. pmid: 32071248. (2022) (Mar. 3, 2020).